

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
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The Role of Law in Transforming the Status of Women in Today's Society

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Abstract

Women have been granted equality of status with men in the Indian constitution and legislation. One of the main characteristics of modern society is a heavy reliance on the law to bring about social change. The emerging trends in Indian society changing the status of Women. Hindu Marriage Act 1955, Maternity Benefit Act 1961, Specific Relief Act 1963, Dowry Prohibition Act 1967, and Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act 1986 are the milestones of the standing position of women. The traditional mindset has been fluctuating and the emerging new social order paved the way for new legislation. The closed room seminars and conferences do not change the attitude of the people. The Community Organisations and Women Organizations should mobilize public opinion and strengthen social efforts against oppressive Institutions like Polygamy, dowry, and sexual harassment and mount a campaign for the dissemination of information about the legal rights of women to increase their awareness. This is a joint responsibility that has to be shared by community organizations, legislators who have helped to frame these laws, and the Government which is responsible for implementing them. This paper studies the status of women as per the reports from 2012-2018.

Keywords: Role of Law, Transforming Status of Women, Today's Society.

Introduction

There never will be complete equality until women themselves help to make laws and elect law makers. – Susan B. Anthony

In India there are numerous laws aimed at empowerment of women in the areas of personal Labour service and criminal and social, economic matters after independence. The fundamental law of the land namely constitution of India guarantees equality for women and empowers the state to adopt measures to positive discrimination in favour of women. "The principle of gender equality enshrined in Indian constitution in its preamble, Part III guaranteed fundamental rights for both men and women, Part IV Directive principles mentioned the fundamental duties for men and women"¹. Article 15 prohibits discrimination on the ground of sex and Article 15 (3) clause gives power to the states for making special provisions for women. Article 16 states the equal opportunity in employment. Article 23 provides prohibition of traffic in human being and forced labour. The 73rd and 74th Amendments in the constitution provided for reservation of seats (1/3) in local bodies of Panchayats and Municipality for women and 84th Amendment reserving 33% for women in parliament and state legislature. One of the main characteristics of modern society is a heavy reliance on law to bring about social change. The surface laws in Indian society changing the status of Women. Hindu Marriage Act 1955, Maternity Benefit Act 1961, Specific Relief Act 1963, Dowry Prohibition Act 1967, Immoral Traffic (prevention) Act 1986 are the milestones of the standing position of women.

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Violence against women and Legal implications

Violence against women defined in the General Assembly Declaration in 1993², “any act of gender – based violence that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women including threats of such acts coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty whether occurring in public or in private life”.

Violation affects the lives of millions of women worldwide in all socio – economic and educational classes. Laws have been used as an instrument of social change and aims to change the status of women from submissive and unequal position. India has made gigantic efforts to herald a good future for women. One of the most significant developments of the post-Independence era is the changing legal status of Indian women and their upliftment through constitutional and other legal rights. As the basic law of the land the constitution puts women on par with men in the matters of civil, economic and political rights.

Of all crimes mentioned in the Indian Penal Code sexual exploitation is the most dehumanising. Singing lewd songs directed at women in public spaces is considered sexual harassment. The offenders could be fined or be jailed up three months or both³. Watching, capturing or sharing images of a woman engaging in a private act without her consent is voyeurism and is punishable⁴. He faces jail term 3-7 years along with fine. In 1986 the Indecent Representation of Women (prohibition) Act was passed to prohibit indecent representation of women through advertisements or in publications, writings, and painting figures or in any other manners⁵. For a first offense the Penalties may be imprisonment upto two years and a fine of upto Rs.2000 subsequent offences would merit a fine of above Rs.10000 and upto Rs.1 Lakh and with imprisonment of not less than six months but not more than five years. In 1990, the National Commission for Women Act has been passed. Under section 3 (1) of the act, the central government shall constitute a body to be known as the National Commission for Women to exercise the powers conferred on and to perform the functions assigned to it under this act⁶. Under the section 10 of the Act investigating and examining all existing provisions of the constitution and other laws affecting women and suggest remedial legislative measures to provide protection to women.

Sexual harassment in the work place is a growing concern for women. Most of the crimes against women related to molestation and harassment at the workplace. In 1997, Vishakha case of sexual harassment at workplace is a case of land mark judgement by Supreme Court of India took a strong stand against sexual harassment⁷. The court also gave detailed guidelines for prevention and redressal of grievances.

Dhananjay Chatterjee was charged with the crimes of rape and murder of Hetal Parekh a 14 year old school girl. On 5th March 1990, he murdered Parekh and escaped to his village. Police captured him on 12th May, 1990. The Sessions Court, High Court of Kolkatta and the Supreme Court of India upheld the conviction and death sentence. Dhananjay Chatterjee was the only person who was judicially executed in India in the 21st century for sexual harassment. The execution by hanging took place in Alipore Central Correctional Home, Kolkatta on 14th August, 2004⁸.

In Delhi Gang Rape case involved a rape and assault that occurred on 16th December, 2012 in Munikka, a neighbourhood in South Delhi. 23 year old female Jyothi Singh Pandey was beaten, gang raped and tortured in a private bus in which she was travelling with her friend, Awindra Pratap Pandey. There were six others in the bus include the driver, all of whom raped and beat her friend. Eleven days after the assault she was transferred to a hospital in Singapore for emergency treatment but died from her injuries two days later. This

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incident generated widespread national and international coverage and was widely condemned both in India and abroad. One convict Ram Singh died in the trial period. Other adults' convicts sentenced to death by hanging. One juvenile defendant served the maximum imprisonment of 3 years under Juvenile Justice (care and protection of children) Amendment Bill 2015 was passed by Rajya Sabha. By the result of this incident Government of Karnataka announced of a 24/7 dedicated helpline 1091 to register sexual abuse complaints from women. The Government of Tamil Nadu announced 13 point action plan to ensure safety for women.

Bhanwari Devi, a social worker in Rajasthan was raped by a gang at a work place. By the impact of this incident Sexual Harassment of Women at Work Place Act, 2013 was passed. It helps women to enhance their rights. According this act the enquiry has to be completed within 90 days.

Eve – teasing is an act of terror that violates a woman's body and self –respect. In Indian term 'eve – teasing' the eve alludes to the biblical story of Eve tempting Adam to stray from the path of righteousness. Teasing is to tempt someone sexually with no intention to satisfying the desire aroused. Both parts of the term put the blame on the women. The Indian media continued use of the euphemism eve – teasing when conversing cases of sexual harassment has to end. The teased or raped girl devastated hopeless and isolated. She was only two choices either she marries the man who raped her or she commits suicide; both to prevent further shame on her family.

There is no uniform law in this country to curb eve – teasing effectively in or with in the public places. Every citizen in this country has right to live with dignity and honour which is a fundamental right guaranteed under Art 21 of the constitution of India. Sexual harassment like eve – teasing of women amounts to violation of rights guaranteed under Articles 14, 15 as well. There was no effective legislation to contain eve – teasing normally complaints are registered under section 294, 354 or section 509 in IPC.

Eve – teasing today has become pernicious horrid and disgusting practice. It occurs mostly around women's colleges, Hotels, schools, in Bus stops, cinema halls and when women travel in buses or trains⁹. In Tamil Nadu, the Prosecution case was that on July18, 1998. Sarika shah, a student of Ethiraj College of Chennai and her college mate were proceeding to a juice shop near the institution when a group of persons came in an Auto Rickshaw and teased them and poured water on the two. He later jumped on Sarika shah as a result of which she fell down sustained head injury and later died. So the Government of Tamil Nadu passed Tamil Nadu Prohibition of Eve – Teasing Act, 1998¹⁰. By this act whoever commits or participate in eve – teasing in any place of Tamil Nadu shall be punished with imprisonment for a term of one year or shall be liable to fine which may extended to Rs.100000 or both¹¹. The Madras High Court on 13th March,2008 upheld a trial court order convicting and sentencing nine persons to five years imprisonment and Justice S.K.Krishnan recommended to the state Government to introduce the a special law could seek remedy from legal forums and legal rights for girls. But the violence still continues.

Durga Amutha from Kanyakumari, Rekha Choudhury in Calcutta, Savitha and Sabitha Sisters were victims of acid attack. Preethi from Madhya Pradesh, Surya of Pudukottai, Nirmala of Chennai were the other victims of eve – teasing. In the year 2014 alone 300 girls were attacked by acid throws. The criminals punished by IPC Section 326 only. After Yamuna acid case the court ordered to pay 3lakhs by two instalments to the victim¹².

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Another category of Eve – teasing is stalking which Indian law has not looked as a serious issue. It is much graver than eve – teasing. It is a neurotic behaviour and civil wrong. Stalking is a repeated harassing or threatening behaviour by an individual such as following person appearing at person's home, person's work place, making harassing phone calls, leaving written messages or objects or vandalizing person's property. A stalker can be imprisoned for a period up to seven years as per Sexual Assault Prevention Bill proposed by the National Commission.

Priya Dharshini Mattoo was a 25 year old law student who was found raped and murdered at her house in New Delhi on January 23, 1996. She struck 14 times with a motor cycle helmet and finally strangled with a wire. Santosh Kumar Singh son of J.P.Singh, Inspector General of Police, her senior in college ad been stalking and harassing her several years and committed crime. In 1995, Priyadharshini complained that Santosh Singh was harassing stalking her. The court handed it over investigation to the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI). But she was raped and murdered at her house on January 23, 1996. The Trial Court failed to give punishment. On October 17, 2006, the Delhi High Court found Santosh Kumar Singh guilty on both counts of rape and murder and on October 30 of the same year sentenced him to death. But in October, 2010 the Supreme Court reduced the death sentence to life imprisonment. But the Indian Parliament has passed Criminal Law Amendment Act 2013, which brought in certain other protective features, such as, section 354 (A) protects women against sexual harassment.

Stalking Murder became the continuous story of Tamil Nadu. S.Swathi was a 24 year old Infosys Employee was murdered on June 24, 2016 at the Nungampakkam Railway station in Chennai, while on her way to her office. P. Ramkumar native of Tirunelveli, stalked Swathi on face book and monitored her movements and murdered. He was arrested after a week on July1, 2016 at Tirunelveli¹³. But he committed suicide on 18th September, 2016 while lodged in Puzhal Central Prison, Chennai. After the investigation XIV Metropolitan magistrate B.C.Gopinath issued an order for formal closure of the case because the victim was died. So, the filed case became useless.

Another stalking stories are 31st June, 2016 Senthil Kumar sets himself on fire embraces Naveena and burns her alive by Villupuram. 13th November, 2017 S. Indhuja (21) and her mother burnt alive by Akashin Adambakkam whose proposal she turned down. On Feburary16, 2018 M. Chitra Devi 14 year old girl in Madurai set ablaze by Balamurugan a relative whose marriage proposal she had rejected. 28th Feburary, 2018, Yamuna (33), a lab assistant died after her lab owner Raja throws acid on her at Madipakkam because she refused the sex harassment. As the latest murder 26 year old stalker Alagesan murdered a college student Ashwini Mohan from Meenakshi College, Chennai in full public view in K.K.Nagar on 09.03.2018 drastically asking her to set his petrol. Soaked body a fire before viciously slashing her throat with a knife¹⁴. He was arrested and put in to the prison. The social organisers and some family members expected the highest punishment to him but her mother didn't want to continue the case because she hesitated to answer the question again and again and not able to spend money.

Wife battering or Domestic Violence is a silent crime against women. It different from any other form of violence against women is that the violence is committed by an intimate partner or his family members living together in a joint family relationship. They suffer in silence rather than complain. Criminologists and the public at large almost completely ignored while battering as a problem until the 1970s. By the middle 1970s the re-

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emergent women's movement made wife battering a central issue and gave it a wide publicity. This evil falls under the general category of assault, under section 319-326 of Indian Penal code¹⁵. High level of family conflict, stress and violence in society, family socialisation in an environment marked by violence, cultural norms and sexual inequalities are noted as cause of wife battering. The bill prepared by Lawyers collective, a nongovernmental organisation is before a group of Ministers to give final shape to this Legislation of the Domestic Violence (prevention) Bill and passed protection of women from Domestic violence Act, 2005.

Under this act the victim can approach the court, which is empowered to pass a 'protection order' to prohibit the respondents from committing acts of domestic violence. A significant aspect of the Bill is that even a friend of the victim can file a petition in the court of relief on behalf of the victim with her written consent¹⁶. But this regulation met with strong criticism because of the likelihood of it being misused. By this emancipation of law Surekha Mote of Bombay case and Shalu Bansals case of Delhi was filed.

Transforming Scenario in Society

The changes in law have definitely titled in favour of women for changing their legal status. But there is a big gap in availing such legal rights and their actual enjoyment. Educational constraints and social backwardness of majority of Indian women accounts for no change in their legal status and their life style in the society¹⁷. Creating awareness of legal rights should be the concern of social workers and NGOs. Women should be courageous to assert these rights in order to mitigate their woes and worries. Media that includes television, radio and newspapers can play a positive role in creating awareness about the pitfalls of violence against women. The government and voluntary organisations are making efforts towards ending or minimizing violence against women and launching various women welfare schemes. In Ramanathapuram the refugee Prasath raped his relative girl and not accepted to marry the girl. She filed a case against Prasath and she submitted the report of DNA test of her baby. So, Prasath was punished with 8 years imprisonment and 31,000 rupees fine by Ramanathapuram Mahila Court¹⁸.

Indian National Bar Association conducted Sexual Harassment Survey on 2018. According the statistics of sexual harassment cases over 68% victims simply do not report their harassment due to the fear of consequences at workplaces¹⁹. Microsoft women filed 238 complaints about discrimination and harassment. However, the laws are passing for the protection of women, the violence against women and sexual harassment also increasing day by day²⁰:

Year	Violence against Women	Sexual Harassment	Rape Cases
2015	155553	338954	1751
2016	18359	39068	2320

Under the Sexual Harassment against Girls and Children Act, 2014 the cases filed against criminals²¹:

Year	Cases filed	Arrested	Punished
2014	1065	1158	65
2015	1544	1869	143
2016	1583	1866	214

In Jan, 2018, 40 year old labour woman was raped by six youths (C. Chetan Meena (21) and others) in Rajasthan's Baran District, who filed a crime and upload a video on social media. The criminals threatened her to kill her family members if she disclosed the matter to

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others. After a month only the victim reported to Mahila Police Station in Baran District on 5th March, 2018. The police have booked six persons under section 376 of IPC. But none have arrested. Another case was filed at Theni District Sessions Court, a college student girl was raped and murdered at Suruli waterfalls near Kambam on May, 2011 by Diwakar He also killed her lover Ezhil Muthalvan. After seven years the judgement was given by Judge Senthil Kumaresan on 7th March, 2018 as death by hanging²².

Another incident was took place in Dhanushkodi on June,2013, M.Malathi stabbing her husband with knife when he attempted to attack her with a cudgel was an act on the spur of the moment and would not fall under the definition of murder. The incident took place in June 2013 and the man died on the way to hospital. Additional District and Sessions Court Judge D. Lingeswaran passed the order of the 5 year old case. She was punished only under 304 Part II of the IPC and imprisonment of 76 days because she was uneducated, dependent on her husband for survival and tolerated the abuses and harassment of not only by her husband and his relatives too²³. Considering the surrounding background and the Judge regretted that “We celebrate the International Women’s Day with a slogan of ‘Press for Progress’ but progress for women in society is a far distance to reach”²⁴ the Judge said.

Without doubt, the scope of women’s career has expanded during the last forty years; it is no longer limited only the household chores. They are now employed in teaching, medicine, law, film, Industry, Public service, fine arts, literature, sport, factories, mines and plantations. The Rural women have been working in the fields and farms. But most increase has been in the employment for woman of the middle class as administrators, telephone girl, sales women and receptionists. But this is only part of the reality. The fruits of progress are not reaching women. The religious practises, scriptures and precepts are still the forces which continue to create women’s existing secondary status in the society. The traditional attitude towards women persists till now.

Closed room seminars and conferences cannot change the society and Legislation cannot by itself change the society. Public opinion has to be moulded to accept these rights. Sometimes judiciary has interpreted new legislation strictly but failed to give the effect to the principle underlying the legislation. It is therefore, necessary not only to pass legislation but also to see that it is implemented. So, Legislative efforts must get social support to realize the ultimate goal gender justice.

Conclusion

The community Organisations, Women Organizations should mobilise public opinion and strengthen social efforts against oppressive Institutions like Polygamy, dowry and sexual harassment, eve – teasing, domestic violence and mount a campaign for the dissemination of information about the legal rights of women to increase their awareness. This is a joint responsibility which has to be shared by community organizations, legislators who have helped to frame these laws and the Government which is responsible for implementing them. At present, there is a conflict between the tradition and emerging new ideas and plodding amendments in law. Once in India domestic violence was not considered as a crime. But now the laws were passed to protect their domestic rights. But, 70% of Indian women accepting her husband torture and domestic violence. Complain allows to take action. But women can’t forward to file case against their husband. ‘Delayed justice is denied justice’. Still 5861 violence against cases for women were unfiled in Tamil Nadu. In Chennai alone 21 criminal cases are waiting for the judgement for the past four years. In total Tamil Nadu 14545 cases are pending. So the people lost their faith in laws. But in somewhere women misused their

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legal rights and filed case against their life partner and his family. At many junctions they are not aware about their legal rights and fear about their future. They are unable to pay cost to get their legal freedom. Even though so many commissions and courts have been established to protect women's rights in the society and they seem to increase with every passing day. The only way to tackle the problem is by creating awareness about the existing rights for women in the society. So educate the Indian women to know about their legal and constitutional rights. Therefore, awakening of the collective consciousness is the need of the day.

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